

Slum Dwellers' Access to Urban Basic Services: A Study of Two Informal Settlements in Dhaka City

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Abstract: This study examines prevalence of slum dwellers' non-access to the urban basic services in Dhaka city. Both the survey and interviews were used to collect information from a randomly selected sample of 30 current slum dwellers comprising both male and female of two informal settlements in Dhaka City. Findings reveal that there are some barriers given the context of Dhaka city. The major barriers identified are: absence of legal entitlements to the land and fear of eviction, supply constraint, lack of infrastructure, knowledge barrier, absence of effective GO-NGO integration, and time barrier including elevated cost. The intervention by the Non-Governmental Organizations has elevated the overall access to basic services. Again the incidence of non-access has been found to be more on female population. The study also finds some remedial measures to overcome the barriers which include; broad based Intervention through GO-NGO integration, legal entitlement to land including removal of constant fear of eviction, awareness build up, cost minimization, removing supply constraint along with time barrier. The current study has taken the initiative of examining two informal settlements which were selected based on two criteria; one is intervention by GO/NGO and the other one male-female population ratio.

Keywords: Slum Dweller; Access, Urban, Basic Services, Informal Settlements, Dhaka City.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background to the Study

Slum dwellers are perceived to be an expression of socio-economic exclusion, which needs to be substantiated by empirical research. Based on the scenario of sprawling slum settlements and availability of services, there are number of literature generations on this issue. Yet, there is a vacuum in assessing the issue, based on the unique and city specific factors. Dhaka being the mega city, needs an immediate focus to resolve the access issues among the slum dwellers who are mostly the informal segment of the workforce. Current paper takes the efforts in political and socio-economic situational updates within the context of intervention and gender dynamics with emphasis on finding barriers to access.

B. Statement of the Problem

Finding the situational updates of the current accessibility within the context of intervention and gender dynamics with special focus on identification of the barriers to access.

C. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to explore the current accessibility situation with relevance to intervention and impact on female segment with specific focus on finding barriers.

D. The Objectives of the Study

- To outline the current state of access to basic services in the settlements.
- To find out the barriers in access to basic services.
- To find out the impacts of intervention in ensuring accessibility of basic services to slum dwellers.
- To find out the impact of inaccessibility to basic services on female population.
- To find out the policy measures to overcome the problems in relation to the access of slum dwellers to basic services.

E. Research Questions

- What is the current state of access to basic services (education, health, sanitation, electricity, water source, Information)?
- Why there is absence of sufficiency in access to basic services?
- What are the impacts of intervention in ensuring accessibility of basic services to slum dwellers?
- What may be the impact of inadequacy of access to basic services on female slum dwellers?
- What measures can be taken to overcome the barriers to access?

F. Research Rationale

The current research is required to present updated access situation of the basic services among the slum dwellers with specific focus on finding barriers to access, given the present context of intervention outcome and gender issues in Dhaka city. The informal settlement expression is inadequately analyzed to bring out contextual barriers in access to basic services which necessitate the current research initiative.

G. Key Terms Defined

• Slums/Informal Settlements

The definition of slums adopted in this paper is that proposed by the UN-HABITAT Expert Group Meeting on slum indicators which states that:

“A slum is a contiguous settlement where the inhabitants are characterized as having inadequate housing and basic services. A slum is often not recognized and addressed by the public authorities as an integral or equal part of the city” (UN-HABITAT, 2002, p. 21; 2003a, p.10).

Slums in this context also include squatter settlements— euphemistically referred to as informal settlements.

• Basic Services

Basic services include water supply, sanitation, power, roads, health and primary education.

• Intervention

The Non-governmental organizations have taken some steps to remove barriers and invested in infrastructural development. These measures are to be termed as intervention. The intervening NGOs which are found to be actively involved are BRAC, DSK and UNDP.

H. Differentiation in Access to Services

Some services conceptually and theoretically are to be made available to all citizens on a uniform basis regardless of income, status or power. Examples include universal free primary education, the fire service, etc. A distinction, thus, is to be made between this universal form of service, and those services where income, position or influence have the capacity to advantage particular individuals or groups. But current research finds that access to both kinds of essential services is affected by financial circumstances.

This is seen by the urban poor as creating different levels of access and situation in which they are disadvantageous from the outset.

I. Access to Services

Accessibility may be conceptualized with six main components:

- Availability,
- Appropriateness,
- Quality,

- Affordability,
- Cultural Acceptability &
- Social accessibility.

Current paper adopted availability, affordability and quality as principle indicators of accessibility to services.

J. Accessibility Quantification

In case of water supply, monetary charge per house, charge/unit for electricity, sanitation establishment cost per house, road access to main roads, health facility in locality and primary education cost per student

K. Social-Economic Origins /Group Identity of the Settlements' Population

The settlement population largely originates from remote rural areas; they have a compelling setting to join the urban workforce. The population has a predominance of female ratio, mostly informal workforce orientation, and a floating socio-economic class origin due to probable pull and push factors.

L. Socio-Spatial Context of Informal Settlements

These are residential areas created by the illegal occupation of land and largely in contravention of official building regulations. Acquisition of the land usually involves planned invasion of unused land whose ownership is unclear and where occupation is unlikely to be opposed or prevented by the relevant authorities. Such settlements have emerged due to the inability of conventional housing markets to cope with the need created by rapid urbanization. Squatter settlements are often found on the urban fringe and in high-risk or vulnerable areas. These settlements are characterized by the absence of basic infrastructure and services, as well as poor quality housing constructed of makeshift materials.

M. Expected Outcome

It is hoped that after having in-depth studies, the current situation will find appropriate expression on the existing accessibility situation in the context of intervention and female vulnerability along with identification of barriers and adoption of policy measures to reduce access problems.

N. Scope of the Study

The study was limited to two informal settlements and mainly based on the set objectives; situational updates of current accessibility situation, the factors determining the accessibility and barriers to access. It was carried out in the months of October to December 2014 engaging the slum dwellers as the respondents to the study.

O. Two Informal Settlements

The very essence of selecting two informal settlements is to analyze the impacts of intervention by NOGO/GO on the accessibility situation. Among the five settlements (Boundary, Chowdhurypara, Kabarstan, Lalmonirhat, and Staff Mahalla) of “Sat Tala” area, I am inclined towards Chowdhurypara and Kabarstan settlements on the basis of two criteria: intervention and female dominance. Chowdhurypara is the icon of intervention by UPPL and

DSK, on the other hand, Kabarstan is predominantly female population dominated and intervention free settlement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter was a review of the existing literature on current and past issues relating to slum dwellers accessibility to urban basic services.

A. Relationship to the Previous Literature

Reports of international agencies such as the World Bank or the IMF are helpful given the ongoing context focusing apparel industries. Recently The World Bank and the International Monetary Fund under their separate lending programmes to boost the country's economic growth asked the government to improve labour conditions and ensure workplace safety in the sputtering apparel industry as we find in the daily newspaper (New Age, October 4th edition). Dhaka being the mega city, needs an immediate focus to resolve the accessibility issues among the slum dwellers who are mostly the informal segment of the workforce. Arimah (2010) summarizes some key factors in determining the accessibility along with pragmatic characterization of informal settlements. Titumir (2004) specified certain barriers in accessibility in the context of Dhaka city which have been deployed in the current paper to analyze the impeding factors in access to services of Dhaka city. World Bank's Dhaka Urban Report (2007) gave an account of service delivery situation in Dhaka city for poorer segment which is comprehensive yet perceived to be incomplete for the scope of current paper. Duflo (2012) also created a model to explain the inaccessibility emphasizing coordination failure as well as legal and institutional issues.

B. Requirement of New Research

The current research is significant since it is a situational update with the inclusion of exploring the determinants and barriers to access basic services. Moreover, it needs to presents new evidence following the existing state of access to basic services based on the intervention and gender issues. The earlier papers mostly lack contextual and spatial reference in explaining city specific expression in exploring the inaccessibility.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology that was used in data collection and analysis. This section consists of the following; research design, study population, instrumentation, procedures and data analysis.

A. Research Design

The study adopted both the qualitative and quantitative research techniques. The descriptive research design was used to carry out the study. The design was to allow the study to obtain a deeper analysis of issues as they happen in the study area. It also allowed generation of unknown issues central to the study topic by highlighting the significance of accessibility to basic services with inclusion of barriers and impacts on the intervention as well as gender vulnerability.

B. Study Population

The study targeted both male and female. The study also included both working and jobless segment. The target population included 30 respondents.

C. Sample Size and Technique

Out of almost a total of twenty thousand target respondents, the study sampled 30 respondents. Out of 30 respondents, 15 of them were male and rests 15 are female.

D. Data Collection Instruments

Data required for the study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary sources allowed the generation of information from the target respondents while the secondary sources emphasized the expression of ideas as presented in previous studies and researches. The primary sources included the use of questionnaires and interviews as methods of data collection while the secondary sources looked at review of previous information relating to the topic.

➤ Questionnaires

This method entailed the design of guiding questions which were asked by the researcher to respondents. The researcher administered the questionnaires to the slum dwellers. A copy of questionnaires attached herewith as Appendix I.

E. Procedure

Appointments/scheduling were made possible prior to the actual date of interviews which enabled the respondents to prepare in advance.

F. Data Analysis

This process involved tabulating, editing and coding data.

➤ Qualitative data

Qualitative data were recorded in the note books. They were then analyzed along the themes of the major variables through subjective analysis as well as narrative analysis. Qualitative data helped the researcher to make a useful interpretation of quantitative data.

➤ Quantitative data

Completed questionnaires were edited at the end of each day to check for consistency and accuracy.

G. Limitations of the study

There were time and financial constraints which acted as limitations specially on the scope and depth of the research. Some respondents were not willing to spare time for the researcher to interview them, thus was difficult to get all the questions answered. This did limit the contents of the information needed for the successful completion of the study.

H. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter provides a detailed description of the results as obtained after data collection. Data is presented in form of tables, based on the objectives of the study namely situational updates, finding determinants, and barriers to access focusing on impacts of gender dimensions in relation to access.

A. Research Question 1

Do you have access to basic services (education, health, sanitation, electricity, water source, Information)?

This section presents the opinions on whether slum dwellers have access to basic services as a whole. The findings are presented in tabular forms.

Table 1 Response of Respondents as to Having Access to Basic Services (all Services Taken Together)

Settlements	Yes		No	
	Respondents	%	Respondents	%
Chowdhurypara	12	80.00	3	20.00
Kabarstan	4	26.66	11	73.33

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 1 shows less than one third slum dwellers availing the basic services at Kabarstan and more than two third are availing at Chowdhurypara and it is an overall assessment considering all basic services which necessarily indicates the positive outcome of intervention.

Table 2 Response of both Male and Female Respondents on Availing access to Basic Services (Gender Discrimination Focus)

Gender	Yes		No	
	Respondents	%	Respondents	%
Male	10	66.66	5	33.33
Female	6	40.00	9	60.00

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 2 shows discrimination in access to services based on gender as two third of male slum dwellers are recipients of basic services, whereas only one third female reported having access to basic services.

Table 3 Responses of Respondents on Access to Services (Item wise) in the two Settlements

Item(s)	Chowdhurypara					Kabarstan				
	Male		Female		Total	Male		Female		Total
	Number	%	Number	%		Number	%	Number	%	
Clean Water	7	87.50	5	71.42	12	3	42.85	1	12.50	4
Electricity	7	87.50	6	85.71	13	2	28.57	0	0	2
Sanitation Facility	7	87.50	6	85.71	13	1	14.28	0	0	1
Primary Education	6	75.00	5	71.42	11	5	71.42	3	37.50	8
Treatment Facility	5	62.50	3	42.85	8	4	57.14	3	37.50	7

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 3 shows that there is a stark difference in between Chowdhurypara and Kabarstan in providing services except primary education(BRAC has intervned in both the settlements), in addition, it substantiates that gender discrimination prevails in access to basic services.

B. Research Question 2

Why there is absence of sufficiency in accessing to basic services?

This section of the research report looks at the probable factorial causes of absence of access to the basic services.

Table 4 Opinion of the Respondents on the Probable Barriers to Access

Barriers	Respondents	
	Number	%
-Absence of legal entitlements to the land and fear of eviction -Supply constraint	15	50.00
-Lack of infrastructure (specially sanitation and heath complex) -Absence of requisite knowledge on own legal and social rights	5	16.66
-Absence of local governance representative -Absence of coordination and GO-NGO integration	20	66.66
-Service delivery time barrier including elevated cost	10	33.33
-Political clout and administration linkage of some intermediaries and class based service delivery		

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 4 lists some barriers as specified by respondents. Majority emphasized on the removal of service delivery including elevated cost. Some of the other significant barriers are: absence of legal entitlements to the land and fear of eviction, supply constraint, lack of infrastructure, absence of requisite knowledge on own legal and social rights, absence

of local governance representative and lack of GO-NGO integration.

C. Research Question 3

What may be the impact of intervention on access to basic services?

Table 5 Opinion on Presence of any External Organizational Assistance for Ensuring Access to Basic Services

Settlements	Yes		No	
	Respondents	%	Respondents	%
Chowdhurypara	15	100.00	0	0
Kabarstan	1	6.00	14	94.00

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 5 shows substantial intervention at Chowdhuripara but almost nil at kabarstan.

Table 6 Opinion about Intervention Outcomes

Intervention Outcomes	Respondents	
	Number	%
- Availability of sanitation facility - Availability of primary School - Availability of water supply - Availability of electricity supply	15	50.00
- Less drug addiction - More income generation of women population	5	16.66

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 6 shows positive outcomes of intervention. The intervention outcomes are mostly the availability of basic services, yet there are other observed outcomes: reduction of drug addiction and accelerated income generation by female population.

Table 7 Responses on Whether there is any Gender Discrimination in Intervention Process

Settlements	Yes		Not sure		No	
	Respondents	%	Respondents	%	Respondents	%
Chowdhurypara	3	20.00	2	13.00	10	66.00
Kabarstan	0	0	10	66.00	5	33.00

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 7 shows no significant gender discrimination in the intervention process at Chowdhurypara, and due to the absence of intervention at Kabarstan, most of the respondents negated or expressed their confusion on the issue.

D. Research Question 4

What are the impacts of inadequacy of access to basic services on female?

This section presents the data over the impacts of non-access on the female dwellers. The findings are presented in tabular forms.

Table 8 Responses of Respondents Whether the Negative Impacts of Non-Access to Services are more on Female

Settlements	Yes		Not sure		No	
	Respondents	%	Respondents	%	Respondents	%
Chowdhurypara	9	60.00	3	20.00	3	20.00
Kabarstan	10	66.66	4	26.66	1	6.66

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 8 shows that the incidence of non-access is more on female dwellers. Almost two third respondents affirmed that female population bears the maximum impacts of non-access to services.

Table 9 Impacts of Inadequacy in Access to Basic Services on Female

Impacts on Female	Respondents	
	Number	%
-More number of child mortality	10	33.33
-Reduced income generation by womenfolk	20	66.66
-Degradation of household health and hygiene	10	33.33
-Increasing female illiteracy	10	33.33

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 9 shows negative outcomes on female segment: more number of child mortality, reduced income generation by womenfolk, degradation of household health and hygiene, and increasing female illiteracy.

E. Research Question 5

What measures can be taken to overcome the absence of access?

This section presents the data on the probable measures as to how to overcome the non-access situation. The findings are presented in tabular form.

Table 10 Response on Suggested Measures

Suggested Measures	Respondents	
	Number	%
-Cost minimization	15	50.00
-Building infrastructural facilities with a special focus on sanitation and health complex	10	33.33
-Knowledge enhancement on own legal and social rights	5	16.66
-Legal entitlement to land and removal of constant fear of eviction	5	16.66
-Quality assurance in service delivery and products	5	16.66
-Removing time barrier in service delivery	5	16.66
-Broad based intervention through GO-NGO integration	5	16.66
-Removal of class based service delivery and political leverage to access	5	16.66

Source: Field Data, 2015

Table 10 shows some suggested measures to overcome barriers. The majority signified on cost minimization, building infrastructural facilities with a special focus on sanitation and health complex, knowledge enhancement, legal entitlement to land and removal of constant fear of eviction. The other responses were: quality assurance in service delivery and products, removing time barrier in service delivery, broad based intervention through GO-NGO integration, removal of class based service delivery and political leverage to access.

V. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the discussion, conclusion and recommendations about the findings. The findings are discussed in relation to the study objectives, case study and literature review.

A. Discussion

➤ Access States

Access to basic services is not adequately available without intervention. There is disparity exists within the service recipients based on gender. Even access to universal services like primary education is not superfluous. Accessibility is based on social hierarchy and it is sometimes income elastic. Discrimination prevails based on the job and social stratification. Political clout and connectivity with the administration are important components to be privileged with.

➤ Barriers to Access

After the interaction with respondents of the two settlements, the researcher identifies the barriers, which include:

- Absence of Legal Entitlements to the Land and Fear of Eviction- It impedes sense of owning and developmental initiative among the settlement populace, which ultimately reduces the negotiation parity.
- Elevated cost- It limits the capacity to avail services by the slum dwellers since access to services is income elastic.
- Lack of knowledge- Knowledge deficient settlement population is not aware of their own rights, hence incapacitated to form alliance and build up pressure on the government machineries.
- Lack of Infrastructure- It creates supply constraints and incapability to provide basic services.
- Time Barrier- It means the service delivery time frame remains within the working hours of the dwellers, consequently limits the efficient distribution of services.
- Absence of Local Governance Representation- The observed absence of City Corporation elected representation halts developmental initiative within the settlements.
- Lack of Coordination and GO-NGO Integration- Central planning and policy initiative aligns with the social stratification and income structure, which is not consistent

with very spirit of the social justice. In addition, absence of broad based GO-NGO integration slows down intervention process as a consequence of conflicting policy focus.

- Supply Constraints- It is the natural outcome of resource limitation, infrastructural weakness, policy failure and mal coordination.

➤ Impacts of Intervention in Access to Basic Services

The intervention is primarily by Nongovernmental Organizations (UNDP, DSK and BRAC). The researcher finds stark difference between the two settlements among which one had intervention and the other didn't. Chowdhurypara being the icon of intervention facilitated the dwellers with the access to basic services mostly free of cost and quality products specially sanitation system. The other one, which is Karbaripara isn't within the integration since central planning lacks consistency in facilitating the NGOs to intervene. Consequently, this settlement is a portrayal of severe lack of access to basic services and devoid of electricity, water supply, sound sanitation and education structures.

➤ Impacts on Gender

The incidence of non-availability of basic services isn't same with the male and female population. The womenfolk carry the most burdens of difficulties in the daily life cycle. The deprivation is manifold in case of female because of their incapacity to movements, financial limitation, social-cultural norms and pregnancy issues. The findings in relation to the negative impacts are: more number of child mortality, reduced income generation by womenfolk, degradation of household health and hygiene, increasing female illiteracy. The reported absence of health complex or difficulty in access to health facilities within means make the womenfolk suffer most during their pregnancy. Degradation of overall health and hygiene causes increased number of child mortality. It also creates hurdles in overall income generation and productivity.

➤ Ways to Overcome

There can be numerous ways but the current paper takes the suggestive measures within the purview of the research outline and findings.

- Broad Based Intervention through GO-NGO Integration- Since intervention proves to be an effective tool for ensuring accessibility, it can be broad based, integrating central planning of the government with non-governmental initiative within the probable framework of Private-Public Partnership.
- Legal Entitlement to Land and Removal of Constant Fear of Eviction- The informal settlements are to be recognized as a socioeconomic reality so that all stakeholders can adopt a feasible approach and there has to be an accepted form of legal entitlements to land. Constant fear of eviction to be removed for ensuring developmental initiative.
- Knowledge Enhancement on Own Legal and Social Rights- Legal and information support may be given to

promote awareness and alliances build up so that they can establish their rights.

- Cost Minimization- May be effective for removing demand constraints.
- Removing Supply Constraint- More governmental investment may spur the supply growth and a public-private Partnership approach may be adopted.
- Removing Time Barrier in Service Delivery- Service delivery time frame may be extended aligning the work schedule of the employed workforce.
- Removal of Class Based Service Delivery and Political Leverage - Class based service delivery should be removed to ensure social justice and equitable access to services.

VI. CONCLUSION

The agglomeration economy of Dhaka city may be enhanced manifold by integrating slums and informal settlements with the mainstream economic drivers. The main working force of the country's economy is accommodated in the informal settlements. Despite the crucial reality of the existence of the informal settlements, the population living in those is severely neglected. Access to basic services is limited. There are number of barriers identified. These are to be removed focusing on the women population. There may be certain remedial measures as identified by the respondents. Though intervention has substantial positive impacts on access situation, yet it needs to be broad based integrating all stakeholders. Legal entitlement, cost minimization, infrastructural development, local governance representation, extension of service delivery hours and awareness buildup may be some of the policy options. An integrated approach towards access to basic services would definitely bring meaningful change in the city economy as well as national wellbeing.

RECOMMENDATION

Given the aforementioned analysis following may be recommended.

- Governmental planning integrating NGO and other stakeholders to provide access to basic services.
- Introducing legal entitlement to land and removing fear of eviction.
- Cost minimization in service delivery to ensure affordability of the service recipients.
- Increased investment by Government in infrastructural development of informal settlements.
- Ensuring timely election and local governance representation.
- Extending daily routine hours of service delivery.
- Providing legal and information support to promote awareness and alliances build up for establishing own rights.

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APPENDIX I

➤ *Questionnaire*

• *Introduction*

This study is intended to provide information on the current situational updates, the effectiveness of intervention, situational impacts on female segment including finding barriers to access. The information provided is purely for academic purposes and is to be treated with utmost confidentiality. I request you to participate in the study by answering these questions please.

✓ *Instructions: Tick the Most Applicable and Fill in the Blank Spaces.*

➤ *SECTION A: Current Accessibility Situation*

A. Do you have accessibility to basic services?

a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

B. Do you have access to clean water?

a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

C. Do you have access to electricity?

a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

D. Do you have access to Sanitation?

a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

E. Do you have access to education for children?

a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

F. Do you have access to treatment?

- a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

G. Is there any discrimination in accessing basic services?

- a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

H. Is there any gender discrimination in case of accessibility to basic services?

- a) Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

I. Is there any external assistance for ensuring accessibility to basic services?

- J. Agree b) Not sure c) Disagree

K. How access is established?

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➤ *SECTION B: Accessibility Determinants*

- State causes/ factors which determine accessibility to basic services.

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➤ *SECTION C: Barriers to accessibility*

- What are the barriers to accessibility?
- What is the most significant barrier to accessibility?

➤ *SECTION D: Impacts of intervention in accessibility*

- Is there any intervention or outside assistance to ensure access to basic services?
- What are organizations involved and how?
- Was the intervention beneficial for all segments of the settlements?
- Was there any gender discrimination in intervention process?
- What would be the probable situation in absence of intervention?

➤ *SECTION E: Impacts of inaccessibility on gender*

- Does inaccessibility situation causes the same effects on male and female segment?
- Is accessibility prevails based on gender equity?
- What is the degree of difference in suffering for male and female segments?

➤ *SECTION F: Ways to overcome*

- Suggest ways to eradicate the barriers to accessibility and to overcome.

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Thank you for participating in this research.

APPENDIX II

Initial Reconnaissance Report

A. Settlement Area : Sattala Slum, Mahakhali, Ward No 20, Dhaka City Corporation.

B. Population : 27 thousands (appx)
70 % female

Mainly day laborers and garments workers

C. City Corporation authority: At present no elected ward commissioner.

D. Selected Settlements: Chowdhurypara (with intervention and less female ratio) and Kabarstan (no intervention and female predominance).

E. Basic Services:

- Electricity -10 tk/unit.
- Water -100 tk/House
- Education -Free
- Sanitation -With intervention.
- Health _ Only one specialized hospital.

F. Intervening Agencies/Organizations

- UNDP (UPPL) : Chowdhurypara.
- DSK : Chowdhurypara.
- BRAC : Chowdhurypara.

G. Dominant segment: Drug dealers and political activists.

H. General income level: 400 taka per day.

I. House rent: Lowest 1600 taka.

J. Contacts:

- Selina, in charge of UPPL.

- Sahidul, Awame League unit secretary, Sattala Basti